

PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF AN ENTREPRENEURIAL CULTURE IN A PERSON

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Annotatsiya. This article in the global times, from the requirements of coming out without men of business, culture and skills formation, this area representatives required that the psychological features about the thought that the comments by mentioned.

Keywords: market, entrepreneur, business and Business Administration, rigor and ingenuity, ability, motivation, success, defeat.

The formation of the motivation of entrepreneurial activity in a person is a link to the formation of the psychology of professional activity. That is, it is the branch of psychology that is directly related to the professional activity of entrepreneurial psychology. It is very broad and diverse, with a spectrum of interests that includes interviewing and staffing, the impact of working conditions on production and the psychological health of workers, career growth, psychological counseling and the study of the behavioral characteristics of people in different professions. Usually the psychology of professional activity is associated with production, but professionals in this area can also be found in other organizations.

Entrepreneurs find original, unconventional ways to achieve an economic, social goal associated with economic risks and implement them. V.I. According to Dalyu, an entrepreneur "should be a capable, determined, bottomless and courageous person, inclined to run an enterprise with large working capital." At

the same time, Dalyu exclaims: "thoughtless entrepreneurship is dangerous." For a young entrepreneur, there should be such quality indicators as a tendency to innovation, the choice of an original path in achieving the goal, knowledge of workmanship and business, the ability to firm and invent, the goal aimed at a high level of use of all opportunities.

Social responsibility is of particular importance for entrepreneurs who are now taking shape in our country. The sociological surveys carried out show that those who began entrepreneurial activities, as a rule, initially proved that the main focus on money, Authority, items and having a fund are considered the meaning of life for them.

Such a one-sided aspiration will not be able to solve social problems, will greatly undermine the base of the economy, and, moreover, will knock out entrepreneurship. Serious changes should be made to such an approach. In all developed countries, the social responsibility of entrepreneurship is of great importance. This problem is also of particular importance for our conditions. Ensuring the fullness of consumer goods in the market is the first task. But some entrepreneurs are trying to make a fortune not by making the market full with goods, but by increasing prices. Whoever knows the rule of Management in entrepreneurship will definitely feel his social commitment. Therefore, in the current period of transition to a market economy, entrepreneurs will have to understand that their interests are inextricably linked with Social Interest and work with a long view.

Western entrepreneurial activities and developments are aimed at a person to make full use of all his capabilities, increase labor productivity, improve the quality of work, achieve high performance of the firm, get more profit.

Studies have shown that there are basically two types of motives that ensure that a person does different things: motives for achieving success as well as avoiding defeat. People are discerned in the course of one or another activity,

depending on which motive they are intended for. For example, people who are inherent only in the motive for achieving success determine such a work with prior confidence that, whatever happens to them, achieving achievement is a higher goal. These people wait for the achievement while they are not yet at work and know that everyone will support them in the takdir, where they started the work in practice. Along the way, they use not only their own strength and capabilities, but also all external capabilities - such factors as familiarity-knowledge, funds.

As we explained above, it is important to clarify the goal at the stage of achieving success from an entrepreneur. The content of the creative approach to life is such that it helps to disassemble the open attitude to any coincidences. It will help the entrepreneur to analyze the goal, choose the most convenient from the available opportunities.

A clear personal goal today requires an entrepreneur who is not satisfied with his work to demonstrate the ability to truly influence him in order to achieve success. If an entrepreneur does not have the opportunity to develop himself and achieve new success, it is necessary to rethink his goal and make a choice. Setting a clear goal is important for entrepreneurs who face difficulties in achieving a balance of satisfaction with entrepreneurial activity.

A different behavior can be observed in individuals who rely on the motivation to avoid failure. For example, they think that before starting something different from the first, they will not suffer defeat at all. Thanks to this, there is a situation in them that is more like pessimism, not believing in achieving an achievement. As a result, they eventually come to the conclusion that "although I am a person who does not walk alone, I am lucky." If individuals of the first category, having successfully completed one work, go to a second job with a Rising Spirit, then representatives of the second category, having completed any

work, will be discouraged, regardless of the outcome, and will enter another job with a feeling of regret.

Solving a problem in the process of entrepreneurial activity has never been easy, but having a certain experience will help you avoid defeat by accelerating the process of achieving the goal. In doing so, we will research three possible ways to achieve the goal, avoiding maglubiyat.

Using a systematic approach to solving the problem. Choosing styles that are suitable for solving various problems. Using people and resources to solve problems. If there is a set of goals, that is, the achievement of success is considered problems associated with development, they cannot be measured by one single criterion. Assessment of the achievement of such a set of goals is carried out step by step.

The seven steps listed below serve as a means of control in achieving success by avoiding defeat:

the first step is preparation;

the second step is the goal;

the third step is the success criterion;

Step Four-information;

step five planning;

step six-practical work;

step seven-practical work improvement analysis.

No matter how illogical it may seem, strict adherence to a previously known rule in achieving success is a useful factor in entrepreneurship. Among the important socio-psychological qualities of an individual in entrepreneurial activity are their attitude to events, that is, to say, in their own language, great suffering, failure, being chivalrous, etc. Especially the entrepreneurs themselves, how they assess their failures, how it happens in them, and how they act in such cases - it is precisely this that is of great importance

Based on the results of the study, it was concluded that entrepreneurs who have experienced a failure and have not yet experienced a failure, give an almost uniform assessment of the level of real risk. There have been some discrepancies in assessing their capabilities in the passage of FAQ difficulties, but this has not yet been proven to the end. It is also worth noting that the presence of major failures does not mean that it can affect the possibility of solving the difficulties facing the entrepreneur.

The development of entrepreneurship directly depends on the assessments that entrepreneurs give to the success of their activities, that is, on personal opportunities and overcoming difficulties in solving the problems they have. A survey of entrepreneurs in 2001 found that while 80% of entrepreneurs overestimated their capabilities, the rest were hesitant to give a clear assessment of their capabilities. So, we can assume that while the vast majority of entrepreneurs assess their capabilities as above average.

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1. Entrepreneurial motivation will depend on motivation in relation to needs in the personality system and the activities that are manifested in the Hulk under their influence.

2. Motivation to strive for success or avoid defeats are important psychological mechanisms that motivate the activities of the personality of entrepreneurs, they have a young, individual and sexual identity.

3. Motivation in relation to entrepreneurship is essentially a social character, which is manifested in a way that directly relates to the individual's attitude to moral norms and values in society and to the spiritual worldview.

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